

COMPETENCIES OF TEACHER-COACHES IN TRACK AND FIELD EVENTS

CARREN A. PANGILINAN¹, DR. KRISTINE PECSON-CINCO²

carrenpangilinan93@gmail.com¹, kristine.cinco@deped.gov.ph²

DepEd Laiya National High School¹; DepEd SDO Lipa City²

Talahiban 1.0, San Juan, Batangas, Philippines¹

Lipa City, Philippines²

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to assess the competencies of coaches in Area IV in Batangas province. This also sought to assess the level of competency of the teacher-coaches in terms of coaching experience, motivation, game strategy, technique, and character building. The researcher identified the constraints met by the respondents in developing coaching competencies. At the end of the study, the researcher was able to come up with a coaching activity that will enhance sports coaching. The study utilized the descriptive method of research with a researcher made questionnaire as the main instrument to gather data and focus group discussion to some of the coaches. The respondents of the study were the 67 secondary public school coaches handling athletics in Area IV Batangas Province. The statistical tools used for data analysis were composite mean, frequency, mean, standard deviation, weighted mean, F-test (ANOVA), and T-test. It was found out that the respondents were moderately competent in the level of competency in coaching experience, very competent in motivation competency, moderately competent in game strategies competency, moderately competent in technique competency and very competent in character building competency. The respondents agreed that the items are the common constraints met in developing coaching competencies in Area IV Batangas province. There is no significant difference on the sports coaching competencies in terms of coaching experiences when the respondents are grouped according to their field of specialization. At the end, the designed program of activities must be implemented at the soonest time possible.

Keywords: Physical Education, coaching competencies, descriptive method, Philippines